

RM¹ FRAMEWORK

D4.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities (PDEC)

HETFFA RESEARCH INSTITUTE LTD.

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**D4.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including
Communication activities (PDEC)**

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¹ Dissemination level:

PU – Public (fully open, automatically posted online on the Project Result platforms);

SE – Sensitive (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement);

CO – EU classified: EU restricted, EU confidential, EU secret under Decision 2015/444.

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List of abbreviations

ALLEA	All European Academies
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation
EC	European Commission
EEAB	External Expert Advisory Board
ERA	European Research Area
GA	Grant Agreement
HEI	Higher Education Institution
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
NDA	Non Disclosure Agreement
PDEC	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities
REA	Research Executive Agency
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RM	Research Management
RMs	Research Managers
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RSO	Research Support Office
RTD	Research and Technological Development
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
UE	User Experience
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This strategy presents the goals, the means, and activities necessary for the successful and impactful communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of the project RM Framework.

In this deliverable, detailed sections address the specific objectives for CDE, along with an overall strategy that includes clustering approaches, clearly defined goals and outputs, and targeted stakeholder groups. This structured approach ensures that each activity is aligned with our strategic objectives and designed to maximise the project's impact.

Activities necessary for successful communication activities is elaborated through detailed roles and protocols, along with the establishment of a robust project visual identity. Key elements of the plan include the website which is comprehensively detailed with its content, structure, and sustainability guidelines as well as the social media strategy and media activities. Then, the planned dissemination activities are presented, such as targeted events, podcast series, that collectively support the project's outreach. Activities paving the way for further use and exploitation of key exploitable results (KERs) are also envisaged through strategic user events, and policy recommendations tailored to drive practical impact.

Finally, performance monitoring is integrated into the plan through rigorous reporting and evaluation mechanisms. The annexes provide comprehensive supporting materials, including the Visual Identity guidelines, Social Media Plan, Podcast Plan, Event Plan, and PDEC Monitoring Table. In conclusion, this document offers clear direction and actionable insights to ensure that the RM Framework remains a sustainable and impactful brand beyond the project's lifespan.

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1. Introduction

The RM Framework's Plan for Dissemination, and Exploitation including Communication activities (PDEC) identifies the main objectives, the relevant target groups, the main channels to reach them out and prepares the basis for tailor-made value propositions. The PDEC is part of WP4, a living document, which is submitted at M3 (D4.1) and it will be regularly updated throughout the project.

This plan provides a comprehensive picture of relevant activities, providing the basis of the subsequent deliverables of WP4, such as D4.2 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication report and D4.5 Business Model and Sustainability Report as well as the successful realisation of CDE activities.

This document incorporates the following tasks and subtasks:

- **WP4 Task 4.1** Awareness and Brand Creation Campaign including Communications
 - Subtask 4.1.1 Visual Design and Identity
 - Subtask 4.1.2 Project Website and social media

This task involves design and communication efforts that boost awareness and engagement by emphasising the project's goals and outcomes. It includes the visual identity that defines the brand of the whole project. It provides concrete specifications for the structure of the website and the schedule of communication channels.

- **WP4 Task 4.2** System Level Approach
 - Subtask 4.2.1 Channel Identification and Engagement Plan
 - Subtask 4.2.2 Impact Assessment
 - Subtask 4.2.3 Value Proposition Definition

These tasks will review previous and existing projects and initiatives to identify what actions and responsibilities are necessary to address the identified stakeholder networks and to create a communications and engagement plan during and post project. Furthermore, it will define the value proposition relying on the results of the impact assessment, the community building and engagement.

- **WP4 Task 4.3** Dissemination, Exploitation and Sustainability
 - Subtask 4.3.1 Development of thematic publications, explanatory cards and videos, monthly podcasts
 - Subtask 4.3.2 Online and face to face public events
 - Subtask 4.3.3 Final Conference and Policy Recommendations
 - Subtask 4.3.4 Business Model and Sustainability Roadmap
 - Subtask 4.3.5 Setting the ground for establishing a European School for Research Management

These tasks all serve the same purpose, to ensure the sustainability and viability of the project in the future, and to lay the foundations for the creation of a permanent organisation to develop research management in an institutional framework.

1.1 Project overview

The **RM Framework** project aims to enhance research management across Europe and beyond by promoting clarity, interoperability, and sustainability in the field of educational and training programmes. It engages a wide range of stakeholders – including national clusters, training providers, funding agencies, ministries, and other RM networks – to establish a common reference framework.

By leveraging extensive networks, the project plans to **standardise training for research managers**, offering both broad European-level programs and specialised initiatives. It will explore various training methods, from community-based and informal approaches to formal university alliances, while respecting national and local differences by involving pilot testers from ten countries.

Additionally, leadership and policymakers will be integrated to align practices with organisational goals and policy frameworks. With a dedicated consortium and a 24-month timeline, the initiative is set to deliver tangible improvements in research assessment, open science, and AI integration. By developing a **quality label** and collaborating with existing networks, the project strives to ensure its long-term impact and sustainability, marking a significant step forward in enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of research management practices.

2. Aims of the PDEC

The PDEC includes all communication activities supporting the work of the project during and after its completion, as well as the dissemination of results to ERA stakeholders. This will contribute to the long-term exploitation and sustainability of the RM Framework training frame and quality label.

The PDEC aims to:

1. Create and maintain the project branding products, promotional materials, website, social network profiles.
2. Engage stakeholders through tailored channels.
3. Communicate success stories and challenges to raise awareness and stimulate debate.

2.1. Communications objectives

RM Framework communication activities will showcase and promote the project, the goals and the findings, results, successes, and impact, starting at the outset and continuing throughout the lifespan of the project, to a wide range of audiences beyond the projects' owned community, including the wider society, the media, and the public. Activities are strategically planned to serve project objectives, and messages are tailored to be of interest to the different communication target groups. Communication main objectives are as follows:

- Raise **awareness** and support about project objectives, relevance, and benefits;
- Develop a **visual identity, website and social media** presence;
- Develop **standard materials** for the consortium partners to use in communications activities;
- Prepare the ground to enhance the recognition of the profession;
- **Communicate** main results, value added and measurable impact to attract future partners.

2.2. Dissemination objectives

RM Framework dissemination activities will promote and prepare the groundwork to transfer the knowledge and results of the project, specifically targeting those audiences which are considered game-changers from the view of recognising professional training programmes, certificates and the profession at large, as well as, international institutional specialists that may

be interested in using the results. Planned dissemination activities are three-folded and tailored to the interests of the different target groups:

- **Reaching out to end-users:** Research Managers and Research Support Office leaders who shall benefit from the project's outputs and use the frame for self-improvement and the enhancement of research support services.
- **Reaching out to training providers** including HEIs, national RM associations, business partners who can enlarge their training offer and potentially use the quality label and the handbook to improve the quality of trainings.
- **Reaching out to RPO leadership, RFOs, policymakers** at national and EU level, **businesses** to recognise the training scheme, the quality label, and the route to professionalisation by presenting the value proposition and the impact.

2.3. Exploitation objectives

Exploitation measures are planned during and beyond the project, aimed at target groups that can make concrete use of results. The exploitation activities in RM Framework have three key aims:

- ensuring the **sustainability** of the RM Framework by building a strong community of users,
- securing the **long-term use and the expansion** of RM Framework results to maintain an integrated and inclusive European frame of trainings and professional development,
- influencing **policymaking** to induce additional measures, instruments and funds reinforcing the professionalisation of RMs contributing to their recognition and enabling the increased competitiveness and performance of institutions and regions across the ERA, with a specific regard to those lagging in R&I.

Planned measures are scaled proportionally to the project's ambition, to help translate project results into its expected outcomes, and contribute to the wider scientific, economic, and societal impacts and contain actions to be implemented during and beyond the lifetime of the project.

2.4. Overall strategy

A comprehensive strategy is essential for successful communication, dissemination and exploitation. To engage wider and targeted audiences, the project will leverage both traditional and digital marketing tools, project management and research methodologies and best practices.

2.4.1 Clustering

Clusters, in the context of Horizon Europe and the broader European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agendas, consist of related projects and initiatives with similar thematic focus and inter-dependent research activities that come together in common actions, events or meetings and share concepts, ideas and problems as well as communication and dissemination activities.

Clustering objectives for RM Framework include from the view of the PDEC are as follows:

- Amplify the reach of communication and dissemination activities;
- Avoid duplication in efforts and confusion in messaging to the same audiences;
- Share information that supports mutual success for projects in the cluster;
- Ensure the exploitation ecosystem is sufficient and robust.

The primary project-project relationship to be established is with RM Framework's 'groundwork' project, "RM ROADMAP (Project 101058475)". Both consortia are willing to work together for the benefit of the RM community where synergies exist, and as the RM Roadmap project is in its final phase and the RM Framework has just been launched, the RM Roadmap experience, communication and exploitation strategies and channels will be useful for sustainability. This includes the following supports:

- RM Framework and RM Roadmap will link to each other's tools and websites where relevant as soon as it is reasonably implementable.
- The RM Framework's social media sites will take over the existing, built platforms of the RM Roadmap in the future, thus ensuring continuity in achieving the common goal of the two projects, which is the recognition and training of the research management profession at European level.

The project is embedded in the broader policy initiatives aiming to strengthen the ERA. **The European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2022-2024 launched by the Pact for Research and Innovation included an action dedicated to Research Management, the so-called ERA Action 17.** It aimed to strengthen the strategic capacity of Europe's public research performing and funding organisations by focusing on upskilling research managers, improving their recognition, enhancing networking opportunities, and building institutional capacity. It addressed challenges like uneven expertise distribution, the need for specialised training, and the lack of formal recognition for research managers. The initiative resulted in important steps paving the way to the recognition of the profession, however, the need for further improvements is indicated by the fact that the Policy Agenda 2025-2027 also includes a dedicated action to the topic, under the title "the new ERA of Research Management".

"Empowering R&I: A New ERA in Research Management" aims to strengthen the recognition and career development of research managers in Europe. It seeks to improve access to training and upskilling tools, including AI guidance, and create a Europe-wide learning and skills development scheme with peer-to-peer learning and mobility. The initiative will promote better networking between public organisations, research funders, and industry to enhance professional development and career paths. Key outcomes include launching a flexible careers framework in 2025, creating a European Charter for research managers in 2026, and establishing an online hub for training and certification under the ERA Talent Platform in 2027. This action addresses the growing need for specialised research management support to boost the efficiency and impact of the European R&I system.

Further initiatives and projects that have the potential to cluster on similar terms with RM Framework, among others, are as follows:

- [foRMAtion](#),

The project foRMAtion developed innovative tools, educational and training methods for the empowerment of students as potential Research Managers through an educational module and mentorship programme. These activities provided the necessary knowledge and skills (both soft and hard) to support their career development. By doing so, foRMAtion aimed to make the profession of research management and administration attractive and raising awareness on the importance of RMAs, contributing to the preparation and implementation of excellent European educational and research projects.

- [EURESTMA](#)

The **EURESTMA** (European Research and Transfer Management) programme is a comprehensive certification initiative designed to professionalise research and transfer management across Europe. Organised by the University of Applied Sciences Osnabrück in

collaboration with leading academic institutions, it combines on-site in Osnabrück, Germany, and/or in Brussels, Belgium, with self-study components. The programme aims to equip research managers with up-to-date tools and methods, foster a pan-European professional network, and enhance institutional strategies in response to evolving research policies.

- [RITrain Plus](#)

RItrainPlus brings together research infrastructures, core facilities, business management schools, and European universities to enhance the management and operation of scientific facilities across Europe. Its objectives include the development of continuous professional development (CPD) courses; establishing a European School for Management of Research Infrastructures (ESMRI) to provide a sustainable foundation for training highly qualified personnel in managing complex scientific operations; and creating a Community of Practice to facilitate peer learning and knowledge sharing among professionals in the field. By implementing these initiatives, RItrainPlus aims to professionalise research infrastructure management, thereby enhancing the efficiency and long-term value of scientific facilities in Europe.

- [CARDEA](#)

CARDEA (Career Acknowledgement for Research Managers) is an EU-funded project led by University College Cork to enhance the visibility and professional development of research managers in Europe. It aims to create a European Competence Framework (RM Comp), develop a Capacity Maturity Model to assess institutional activities, and establish a training and networking hub. CARDEA seeks to standardise skills, support career progression, and strengthen the role of research managers in the EU.

- [RAPIDS](#)

The project seeks to develop an objective tool - the Research Administration Professional IDentity Values Scale (RAPIDS) - to measure the professional identity of Research Administrators (RAs) globally. This will enhance recognition of the profession and support its growth. Using a mixed-methods approach, including literature review, interviews, focus groups, and surveys, the project aims to create and validate RAPIDS. The scale will help current and aspiring RAs, professional associations like NCURA, and policymakers better understand and strengthen the field's core values and identity.

- [MAPIT](#)

MAPIT – M(obilizing) A(dvanced) P(artnerships) for Digital I(nnovation) and T(ransformation) – bridges the gap between innovative SMEs, research entities, and European R&I networks, fostering sustainable international partnerships. By establishing digital innovation centres and upskilling R&I managers, MAPIT strengthens university-industry collaborations, promotes internationalisation, and empowers research entities to thrive within Horizon Europe and the European Research Area.

- [V4WB RMA Network \(Plus\)](#)

The project V4+WB RMA Network Plus aims to further reinforce the network of Research Support Professionals, or in short, Research Managers and Administrators (RMAs). Through intensified knowledge exchange and capacity building activities it will contribute to the increased competitiveness of the Visegrad Four and Western Balkan countries in Research and Innovation.

2.4.2 Goals and outputs

The PDEC defines targets, protocols, and schedules for relevant activities.

- ➔ The main **communication** goals are to raise awareness, and its significant outcomes include a well-structured branding campaign, visual identity, and online presence.
- ➔ The main task of **dissemination** is to identify and engage stakeholders. The result is an effective value proposition.
- ➔ **Exploitation** is about making the best use of project results by, but most importantly, beyond the consortium, involving the right stakeholders.
- ➔ For the RM Framework, one of the most significant sustainability objectives is setting the ground for establishing a European School for Research Management.

Goals and outputs			
Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation	Sustainability
Branding	Identifying stakeholders	Prepare the use of KERs	Policy Recommendations
Visual identity	Engaging stakeholders	Online and offline events	Business model
Awareness campaign	Impact Assessment		Sustainability
Online presence	Value proposition Definition		European School of RM

To achieve the project's objectives, we use the following tools and channels:

Tools and channels		
Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Visual identity	Targeted mailshots	Targeted actions for RPO Leadership
Website	Website	Explanatory user cards
Social media	Focus groups	Targeted RM Events
Outreach Events	Targeted RM Events	Policy recommendations
Podcast	Podcast	User Events
Videos	Videos	Final conference
Media coverage	Final conference	
	Scientific publications	
	Posters	
	Outreach events & user events	

2.4.3 Target groups

The RM Framework consortium has initiated a process to develop a strategic approach to each category/audience, and to list key stakeholders within each category. Stakeholder mapping actions taking place under WP4 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation in Subtask 4.2.1 Channel Identification and Engagement Plan. As it is identified by that subtask, stakeholders can be grouped according to the type of target as follows:

- **End-users:** RMs, Potential RMs, RSO leaders, HEI students including PhD students, Support offices of RPOs, Scientific and Research Community who shall benefit from the project's outputs and use the frame for self-improvement with a special regard to professional development, and to improve research support services.
- **Training providers:** HEIs and adult learning organisations including umbrella organisations, associations of teachers as well as RM associations, business partners who can enlarge their training offer and potentially use the quality label.
- **Leaders:** RPO & HEI leadership, responsible for making strategic decisions at an organisational level. Decision-making stakeholders: RFO, policymakers at the national and EU level, and businesses and professional associations to recognise the training scheme, the quality label, and the route to professionalisation by presenting the value proposition and the impact.
- **Broader Audiences:** General Public and Civil Society, Media and Press, Scientific and Research Community.

Another way of segmenting the target groups could be to classify them in line with the main goals of the PDEC:

Target groups		
Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Community of professionals in RM across the ERA	Training providers (HEIs, national/ European RM associations, business partner)	Training providers (HEIs, national/European RM associations, business partner)
Students or professionals in other fields as potential future RMS	Leaders (RPO & HEI leadership)	Leaders (RPO & HEI leadership)
General public & civic society In Consortium Countries, the wider EU & international	End-users (RMs, Potential RMs, RSO leaders, HEI students)	End-users (RMs, Potential RMs, RSO leaders, HEI students)
Media & Press	Decision-making stakeholders (RFO, policymakers)	Decision-making stakeholders (RFO, policymakers)
Policymakers and decision-makers and RFOs	Boarder audiences (scientific and research community)	
Business stakeholders		

2.5. Responsibilities of partners

While WP4 leader HETFA is responsible primarily for the proper and impactful implementation of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, by doing so, it strongly relies on the contribution of WP leaders, Task leaders, and the rest of the consortium. All HETFA colleagues are available through the shared e-mail address: rm-framework@hetfa.hu.

Therefore, it is crucial to clearly identify colleagues responsible for communication, dissemination and exploitation by each partner, affiliated entities, and associated partners. The relevant contact table is available on SharePoint WP4 folder. Having a direct contact between WP4 leader and each entities' communication managers is one of the basic requirements of smooth communication and share of information.

As it is described below, HETFA will create several samples materials and press releases to help partners in communicating about RM Framework, however, all partners are invited to contribute with any relevant ideas. WP leaders and Task leaders have special responsibility to work closely with HETFA in planning and carrying out the various CDE activities.

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3. Communication Plan

General communication to the broad audience

RM Framework communication activities will showcase and promote the project, the goals and the findings, results, successes, and impact, starting at the outset and continuing throughout the lifespan of the project, to a wide range of users beyond the projects' owned community, including the wider society, the media, and the public.

The subsequent section provides a detailed overview of the following elements:

- Roles and protocols for project communication
- The project visual identity
- Website
- Social media
- Press and media

The following communication measures and tools will be used: videos, brochures, visuals promoted through social media, newsletters, and networks. These will focus on the training framework and quality label, highlighting the added value and impact for RMs, training providers, RPOs, and RFOs.

3.1. Roles and protocols

As WP4 leaders, HETFA has general responsibility for managing communications activities. The following roles and protocols apply to the communication procedures for all consortium partners throughout the RM Framework project:

- Communication is talking to the outside world about the project, using information already in the public domain.
- Compliance is governed by Article 17 and Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement; partners must:
 - acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate); the EU flag must be at least as prominent as other logos.
 - include the disclaimer: “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.”
 - If communication is expected to have “major media impact”, the coordinator must be notified so they can inform the Project Officer in advance.
- Presentation slides, poster designs for printing and videos will be provided to be used by the partners without needing further permission.
- In order to coordinate, promote and support compliance in communication activities, partners should notify the WP4 lead as soon as a communication activity is planned, by emailing rm-framework@hetfa.hu.
- To multiply the benefit of individual activities, take photos and videos which can be used for other content (e.g. newsletter, social media).
- Following the activity, partners are required to update or complete the project tracker;
 - Add/confirm details including date, location, audience type and size.
 - Report social media campaigns (a significant post or series of posts clearly linked to the project on your own channel) as a single activity; ensure that you have access to the reach statistics.

- Partners are required to record specific costs related to these activities, as they will be requested with the financial report.

3.1.1. Project visual identity

An early task in the project (M3) is the development of an identity for the project – comprising a logo, document and PowerPoint templates.

The RM Framework logo is presented below. The primary colour used is indigo purple, secondary is teal blue and complementary shade is orange, light green and light yellow.

The visual concept extends the RM Roadmap brand, maintaining continuity through the bold colour scheme, the use of the "RM" abbreviation in the logo, and a similar font. It represents both the continuum with RM Roadmap but also the main aim of the project, namely, framing the RM trainings across Europe. In the RM Roadmap logo, the "RM" letters are designed as road markings, whereas in the RM Framework logo, "RM" is enclosed within a road marking frame.

A set of slides using this identity containing project information is provided that can be used without further additional permission and will be maintained and updated as RM Framework progresses. Additional details regarding the project's visual identity, such as the fonts and colours to be used in print and digital material, and templates for documents and PowerPoint presentations, are attached in *Annex 1. – Visual Identity*.

As described in the protocol above, the reference to EU funding must be indicated next to the logo: acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate); the EU flag must be at least as prominent as other logos.

3.2. Website

During the initiation phase, the RM Framework website is required to display information about the project and the partners, and to encourage visitors to engage with the project by following social media accounts and/or providing contact details for newsletters and direct communication. The project's website, located at www.rm-framework.eu will go online in April 2025 (M3).

3.2.1. Website content

The website includes key information on the project, such as:

- Project description/scope;
- Objectives;

- Partners and their information;
- Results – a dedicated space will be created where results and deliverables can be accessed and downloaded;
- Dedicated content for target groups (see details below);
- News and events – all partners will regularly send articles showcasing their progress and detailing where they have presented or published project-related work.

Dedicated content on the website for the target groups			
Research Managers	Education and Training Providers	Leadership	Policymakers
Quality label	Handbook	Quality label	Impact assessment
Pilot cases	Teaching methodology	Pilot cases	Value Proposition
Training providers	Quality label	Impact assessment	Recommendations
	Pilot cases	Value Proposition	Policy briefs
	Mentoring	Recommendations	

Moreover, the dedicated website content for the target groups is considered a living document; while it initially outlines the identified key results, these are regularly reviewed and updated in collaboration with the project partners.

3.2.2. Website structure

Header and menu points of the RM Framework website:

RM FRAMEWORK					
Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area					
About	News & Events	Target Groups	Results	Contact	↗ RM Roadmap

3.2.3. Website sustainability

To keep the website updated with the project’s latest news, each partner will send content, including brief articles on where they have presented or published information about the project, when relevant to rm-framework@hetfa.hu. These articles should be between 150-250 words and should be accompanied by a photo of at least 200x300 pixels and, if applicable, links or PDFs with additional information. The project website will be maintained for at least five years following the end of the project so that stakeholders can continue to get information about the project.

The website will follow the latest digital trends, aiming for excellence in both user interface (UI) and user experience (UX). Thanks to search engine optimisation (SEO), it will be easily

discoverable through relevant keywords. Website traffic will be monitored using Google Analytics.

4. Social media

Social media platforms will be utilised to enhance awareness among individuals unfamiliar with the project and to reinforce its identity among those already engaged. The project plan proposed three social media channels would be established:

- LinkedIn,
- YouTube,
- Spotify.

Considering the experience of partners currently engaged in other Horizon actions, the consortium agreed that Facebook, Instagram, and X (Twitter) were no longer appropriate or worthwhile platforms for the RM Framework.

The operational concept of the three selected platforms was developed with a focus on sustainability and continuity:

- A new **LinkedIn** page will not be created; instead, the existing RM Roadmap page will be transferred and adopted. During the project overlap period (February 1, 2025 – August 1, 2025), the channel will be renamed **RM Roadmap & Framework** to support the transition phase and the long-term continuity. In this interim phase, the RM Roadmap will focus on the dissemination of results, while the RM Framework will prioritise enhancing brand awareness.
- The **Explanatory Videos** will be published on the **EARMA YouTube** channel, where the video content of the RM Roadmap has also been featured. As a result, this YouTube channel serves as a unifying platform and an archive for HEU projects related to RM.
- A series of **podcasts** will be produced as part of a collaboration with **The Grant – The EU Funding Podcast** channel. The series will include 15-18 podcasts lasting for ca. 30 minutes will start from giving an overview on the current state of professional development and the relevance of standardised training programmes in Research Management and then scoping down to the main results of the project. The exact topics and content of the podcasts will be co-created by WP and task leaders who will also appoint the experts participating in the podcasts.

Dedicated tables are included in *Annex 2. – Social Media Plan* and made available in SharePoint WP4 folder to develop and ensure the consistency of social media activities. For that reason, separate tables are developed for the social media activities, the explanatory videos, and the podcasts (*Annex 3. – Podcast Plan*). All WP and task leaders are responsible for constantly providing inputs by sharing updates on the work done, giving summaries on achievements and related activities.

Social media platforms			
Platform	Concept	Content	Management
LinkedIn	Continuation of the RM Roadmap page	Short summaries	HETFA
YouTube	We will use the EARMA YouTube channel	Videos	HETFA, EARMA & WP leaders

Spotify	We will collaborate with a podcast channel called <i>The Grant – The EU funding podcast</i>	Podcasts	HETFA and WP leaders
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In order to organize content, increase discoverability, and boost engagement, the following hashtags will be used for RM Framework related posts: #RMframework #researchmanagement #researchmanagers #RMtraining #HorizonEU #RM

5. Press and media

An initial press release at project kick-off was featured in [Research Professional](#) and posted to the [WP4 coordinator](#), the [coordinator's website](#) and several partner websites. Further media engagement will follow project activity. The main targets are the relevant research business publications at EU level, such as Research Professional News and Science Business, and at national levels as well. Popularised science publishing platforms (Horizon Magazine, The Conversation) may also be appropriate. Press releases, print interviews / articles will be pursued for coverage of project aims and results in media, primarily focused on the consortium countries involved, but with an international orientation as well.

RM Framework: Advancing Research Management Training Across Europe

Mar 25, 2025 | Division for International Cooperation, News, RMA

Objectives:

- Inform about project results, use and benefits by translating the results into measurable economic, societal and scientific impacts
- Raise awareness about project objectives and relevance to all the sectors involved

Measures:

- Press releases, print interviews / articles will be pursued for coverage of project aims & results in media.
- Primarily focused on the consortium countries involved, but with an international orientation as well.

6. Dissemination activities

RM Framework dissemination strategy will promote and prepare the groundwork to transfer the knowledge and results of the project. Dissemination actions will also be supported by the broad and well-established network of partners and previous projects and backed by Open Science measures, and the DMP.

6.1. Roles and protocols

As WP4 leader, HETFA has general responsibility for reporting on dissemination activities. Disseminating of own results in compliance with the following protocols is the responsibility of each partner.

- Dissemination is sharing the results of the project outside of the consortium in a publicly available format.
- Results are: *"Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights"*.
- From the Grant Agreement, Article 17 states the obligation to disseminate, further detailed on Annex 5 describing Open Science protocols.
- Dissemination is subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests; therefore, additional provisions are contained in the Consortium Agreement - these are to allow publication, not prevent it.
- Dissemination can be by any means: **journal articles, conference presentations, white papers** etc.
 - For journal articles and conference submissions where the full article is submitted for peer review, send the final version of the article to rm-framework@hetfa.hu at least 30 days in advance of publication.
 - A formal notice is sent to all partners containing the submission, with a deadline for objections no less than 30 days later.
 - Objections must be specific and have corrective actions; i.e. either:
 - Remove confidential information.
 - Identify details that could prevent successful exploitation project results, needing a delay of up to 90 days to put protection in place.
 - With no valid objections, the publication can proceed.
 - For conferences where only an abstract is submitted:
 - If the abstract discloses project results, you must share it for review as per the above process prior to submission.
 - If the abstract only describes in general what will be presented, ensure a description of the content of your presentation is shared for review according to the above timelines prior to the actual presentation or event.
 - In all cases, discuss planned dissemination with the project partners at appropriate meetings well in advance.
- On Open Access for publications:
 - All peer-reviewed scientific publications relating must, at the latest at the time of publication, have the final peer-reviewed manuscript deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.

- Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to their articles to be able to comply.
- Only publication fees (“APCs” – Article Processing Charges) in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for claim under the project.
- The Directory of Open Journals lists compliant venues for publishing.
- On Open Data:
 - Governed by the Data Management Plan (D5.2).
- Other:
 - Follow the CRediT (Contribution Roles Taxonomy) for authorship.
 - Abide by the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment principles, in particular with respect to journal metrics.

6.2. Channels

The dissemination activities will be designed to ensure broad engagement with key stakeholders and maximise the impact of the project's outcomes. A **co-creation exercise** will bring together **training providers, higher education institutions (HEIs), research-performing organisations (RPOs) leadership, and research funding organisations (RFOs)** to collaboratively refine and enhance the training framework.

To facilitate knowledge transfer, a **podcast series** will be launched, explaining the various components of the training framework and the quality label in an accessible format. Additionally, the project's findings and impact will be communicated through **scientific publications and posters**, highlighting the added value of the training framework.

Finally, a **final conference** will be organised to showcase all project outputs, accompanied by **policy recommendations** targeted at decision-makers and relevant stakeholders. This event will serve as a platform to present key findings, foster discussions, and support the long-term adoption of the training framework.

Below is the plan for the dissemination of project results. Please note that given the living nature of this document, workshops will be held with partners where the list of project results relevant for dissemination will be regularly revised and adjusted.

Dissemination			
Measure	Target group(s)	Tools/ Channels	Time frame
“Good practice” RM training manual	Training providers including HEIs, national/European RM associations, business partners	Website, newsletter, social media, events, explanatory user cards	M12 onwards and beyond the project
Mentoring and train-the-trainer qualification for RM training providers manual	Training providers including HEIs, national/European RM associations.	Website, newsletter, social media, events, explanatory user cards	M12 onwards and beyond the project

Handbook on the RM training approach	Training providers including HEIs, national/European RM associations.	Website, newsletter, social media	M12 onwards and beyond the project
Quality Label and assessment method	Training providers including HEIs and national/European RM associations, business partners, RPO leadership, RFOs, Research Managers and Research Support Office leaders	Website, targeted mailshots, social media, user events, conferences, explanatory user cards	M20 onwards and beyond the project
Case studies, Value Proposition, Impact assessment & Policy Recommendations	Training providers including HEIs and national/European RM associations, business partners, RPO leadership, RFOs, policymakers	Website, targeted mailshots, social media, user events, conferences, explanatory user cards	M22
Explanatory Videos & Podcasts	Research Managers and Research Support Office leaders, training providers including HEIs and national/European RM associations, business partners	Social media, YouTube & Spotify, targeted mailshots, website	M12 onwards and beyond the project
Workshops, presentations at related events	Research Managers and Research Support Office leaders, training providers including HEIs and national/European RM associations, business partners, RPO leadership, RFOs,	Holding dedicated workshops/presentations to present project results at conferences and events organised by national/European RM associations, events of Rectors' Conferences, University Alliances, R&I days, etc.	M7 onwards
Peer-Reviewed Scientific Publications and Posters	RM and scientific community, leaders of Research Support Offices and RPOs	Scientific journals & other respected specialist media (Open access)	M13 onwards
Final Conference	Policymakers, RMs and identified stakeholders in academic, communities, and local governments	Conference with seminars, lectures, and demos on the results of the project overall	M24

6.3. RM Framework's appearance in newsletters

RM Framework does not intend to issue newsletters to avoid overloading the relevant target groups and stakeholders. However, partners will be actively publishing news about the project in regular newsletters issued either by their organisations, initiatives or projects. This will facilitate both communication and dissemination efforts.

Press releases and key informational packages will be shared with partners to be included in the newsletters, regarding key project updates, upcoming events, and relevant research findings, to ensure effective stakeholder engagement and dissemination. Each partner is required to return a proof of publication, confirming that the news has been shared via their own media channels. These reports will be stored in the press monitoring table, which is included in *Annex 5 – PDEC monitoring table*.

6.4. Events

During RM Framework two main outreach events and a series of user events are envisaged, as described in the table below. Partners will also participate in national/European/international research management conferences, seminars, and workshops and will also endeavour to represent RM Framework at regional meetings and events, to convey the regional dimension of the project and potential links to Regional Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3).

Events			
Event type	Target group	Content	Time frame
Workshops, presentations at related events	RMs and RSO leaders, training providers including HEIs and national/European RM associations, business partners, RPO leadership, RFOs	Holding dedicated workshops/presentations to present project results at conferences and events organised by national/European RM associations, events of Rectors' Conferences, University Alliances, R&I days, etc.	M7 onwards
Online user events	RMs and RSO leaders, training providers including HEIs and national/European RM associations, business partners, RPO leadership, RFOs	Preparing exploitation of the project output and results	M13-M24
Offline user events	RMs and RSO leaders, training providers including HEIs and national/European RM associations, business partners, RPO leadership, RFOs	Preparing exploitation of the project output and results	M9-M24
Outreach events	All communication target groups	Holding dedicated workshops/presentations to present project results	M9-M24
Final Conference	Policymakers, RMs and identified stakeholders in academic, communities, and local governments	Conference with seminars, lectures, and demos on the results of the project overall	M24

Outreach and other events (incl. joint events with other projects working for the recognition and widening the training offer in the field of RM; events of national and European associations/networks/platforms of RMs; European R&I days, European Week of Cities and Regions, open days/fairs organised by universities or RFOs or ministries/agencies responsible

for education, R&I, events of university alliances, etc.) aimed at all communication target groups. A more detailed event plan will be jointly developed in the *Annex 4 – Event Timetable*, where the date, venue, format, and type of the events are also specified.

7. Exploitation activities

Exploitation measures are planned during and beyond the project, aimed at target groups that can make concrete use of results. During the project's lifetime, workshops will be organised where partners will identify and regularly revise the list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and develop the necessary strategies to ensure the long-term usage of these results.

RM Framework exploitation tools and channels will include:

- **Targeted actions** for RPO Leadership.
- **Targeted RM Events:** project partners will attend diverse conferences, workshops both online and offline organised by professional associations and networks where they will present the project and relevant results.
- **Explanatory user cards** on diverse components of the training handbook, teaching methodology backed by the results of the value proposition and the impact assessment,
- **Online and offline user days** dedicated to RPO leadership, RFOs, RSO leaders and RMs, to facilitate the adoption and adaptation of the trainings to national/local circumstances,
- **Final conference** with seminars, lectures, and demos on the results of the project overall for policymakers, RMs and identified stakeholders in academic, communities, and local governments.

7.1. Roles and protocols

As WP4 leader, HETFA have general responsibility for exploitation planning and management.

- Exploitation aims to ensure the long-term use of the results by the consortium and beyond, including among other things, both commercial and non-commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process, creating, and providing a service, standardisation or policy-making activities, developing methodologies, providing trainings and further research and innovation actions.
- As defined earlier for dissemination, results are: *"Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights"*.
- Provisions for Joint Ownership of results are found in the Consortium Agreement: Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement states that:
 - ○ funded beneficiaries must — up to four years after the end of the action — use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.
- Adding Results to the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) is the responsibility of the coordinator, and may require following the Dissemination protocols in the previous section.
- The HRP accepts only Key Exploitable Results (KERs), defined as Results selected due to high potential to be exploited, based on degree of innovation, availability, and potential impact.

7.2. Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The project is supposed to deliver tangible results in the rapidly evolving landscape of research assessment, open science, and AI integration. Moreover, by developing a quality label and fostering collaboration with existing networks, the project seeks to ensure long-term relevance and sustainability beyond its duration. Ultimately, the RM Framework project represents a critical step towards enhancing the effectiveness, efficiency, and impact of research management practices across Europe and beyond.

We will rely on the methodology developed by the Horizon Result Booster services in the identification of the KERs and the development of unique value propositions and exploitation plans for each.

The KER identification methodology table, developed by the META Group in the frame of the Horizon Results Booster services, will be completed collaboratively from M12 on a half yearly basis by the partners. Through dedicated workshops, we will collectively identify the KERs and work together to fill out the table, which will serve as a foundation for the development of the Exploitation Strategy.

Identification of the KERs by HRB methodology	
Problem	Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your “Customers”.
Alternative solution	Describe how your “customer” has solved the problem so far.
Unique Selling Point (USP) - Unique Value Proposition (UVP)	Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?
Description	Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e. product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.
"Market" – Target market	Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?
"Market" – Early Adopters	Early adopters are the “customers” you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others. (they are not the project partners).
"Market" – Competitors	Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?

Go to Market – Use model	Explain what is your “use model”, how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.
Go to Market – Timing	What is the time to market?
Go to Market – IPR Background	What is the Background (type/ partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.
Go to Market – IPR Foreground	What is the Foreground (type/ partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.

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8. Performance monitoring

To plan and monitor the performance of successful CDE activities, a shared platform is essential, where everyone can see the progress and the schedule. Therefore, HETFA as WP4 leader developed diverse tables, such as the Social Media Plan, Podcast Plan, Event Plan, and PDEC Monitoring Table. These tables are available on SharePoint, WP4 folder. The role of partners is defined as it follows:

- Social Media Plan: each partner is encouraged to contribute and co-create the content of social media appearances,
- Podcast Plan: WP and task leaders shall contribute to the planning and implementation,
- Event Plan: each partner is encouraged to contribute and take care of certain events,
- PDEC Monitoring table: each partner shall update it continuously, but at least on a monthly basis, if relevant.

The website traffic will be monitored by HETFA through Google Analytics. If it does not generate the desired numbers, a review of the SEO will be necessary.

To implement rigorous and efficient monitoring mechanism, the following indicators were defined during the preparations of the project proposal. Given the living nature of the PDEC, half-yearly checks, and if necessary, relevant actions and adjustments will be defined by WP4 leader and WP leaders.

Communication KPIs		
Communication	KPIs/Impact	Time frame
Visual identity & specific branding of the quality label	Guidelines created and shared with Partners	M3 onwards and beyond the project
Website	Website launched. >240 Visits per month	M3 onwards and beyond the project
Social media	Social media accounts launched & active. At least two posts per week.	M3 onwards and beyond the project
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 online user events (M13- M24) • 10 offline user events - 2 combined with the outreach events, and 8 at national levels (1 per partner country) • 2 outreach events (at mid- term connected to the Budapest events & 1 at the end connected to the final events) • 8 participations at other events per year 	M1 onwards
Media coverage	By end of the project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 press releases/partner country, • 6 printed articles/interviews in total 	M6 onwards

Dissemination KPIs		
Tools	KPIs/Impact	Time frame
“Good practice” RM training manual	120 Downloads	M12 onwards and beyond the project
Mentoring and train-the-trainer qualification for RM training providers manual	120 Downloads	M12 onwards and beyond the project
Handbook on the RM training approach	120 Downloads	M12 onwards and beyond the project
Quality Label and assessment method	240 Downloads	M20 onwards and beyond the project
Case studies, Value Proposition, Impact assessment & Policy Recommendations	80 downloads	M22
Explanatory Videos & Podcasts	40 views/listens per month	M12 onwards and beyond the project
Workshops, presentations at related events	8 participations at other events per year	M7 onwards
Peer-Reviewed Scientific Publications and Posters	2 peer-reviewed articles (non-desk rejection) and 4 posters presented at conferences	M13 onwards
Final Conference	200 attendees	M24

9. Conclusions

In conclusion, the PDEC provides a comprehensive and detailed description of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities throughout the entire duration of the RM Framework project and beyond. It outlines the distinct roles and protocols, the objectives, and the tools and channels employed to ensure the success of the related initiatives. In addition, it covers related projects, the visual identity, and performance monitoring.

These activities will present and emphasise the added value and impact of RM Framework for research managers, training providers, RPOs, and RFOs.

To ensure the efficiency and sustainability of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities and to maintain the RM Framework as a viable brand even after the project's conclusion, it is of crucial importance that partners take ownership for these activities, work in continuous collaboration, provide mutual support, and stick to regular reporting.

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10. Annexes

10.1. Annex 1. Visual Identity

10.1.1. RM Framework logo

10.1.2. RM Framework Colours

Primarily colour		Indigo	R:42, G: 36, B: 110
Secondary colour		Teal	R: 112, G: 193, B: 200
Other colours		Orange	R: 246, G: 166, B: 68
		Light Green	R: 190, G: 221, B: 204
		Light Yellow	R: 254, G: 233, B: 139

10.1.3. RM Framework Templates

Three templates have been designed for RM Framework and will be sent to partners and made available for download on SharePoint, in WP4 folder. These elements must be strictly adhered to by the RM Framework consortium.

1. The “**Presentation Template**” has been designed for presentations at project meetings and for official presentations on behalf of the RM Framework project (e.g. during conferences or other events).
2. The “**Deliverable template**” has been designed for project reports, outputs and deliverables.
3. The “**Letterhead paper**” has been designed for any project related official document.

10.1.4. RM Framework Typography

Arial Nova is our primary typeface that should be used in all typeset communications, such as publications, leaflets and reports. It should also be used for all printed communications (letters, forms, etc.). This font was chosen for its clean lines and ease of readability. For the titles, Arial Black can be also used.

Title: Arial Black, font size 24, bold, indigo

Heading 1: Arial Nova, font size 14, bold, indigo

Heading 2: Arial Nova, font size 12, bold, indigo

Heading 3: Arial Nova, font size 11, bold, indigo

Paragraphe: Arial Nova, font size 11, normal, black

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10.2. Annex 2. Social Media Plan

The Social Media Plan is available at the WP4 folder on SharePoint: [RM Framework social media_podcasts_events.xlsx](#)

SOCIAL MEDIA TIMETABLE AND CONTENT PLAN _ TEMPLATE					
Nr	Topic	Aim	Partner responsible	Content	Link
Week 1					
Week 2					
Week 3					
....					

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10.3. Annex 3. Podcast Plan

The Podcast Plan is available at the WP4 folder on SharePoint: [RM Framework social media podcasts events.xlsx](#)

PODCAST TIMETABLE AND CONTENT PLAN _ TEMPLATE							
Podcast Nr.	Timing of the release	Topic	Aim	Responsible partner	Interviewee 1	Interviewee 2	Timing of the recording
Podcast 1	Week of 26 Aug						
Podcast 2	Week of 6 Oct						
Podcast 3	Week of 17 Nov						
Podcast 4	Week of 15 Dec						
Podcast 5	Week of 26 Jan 2026						
Podcast 6	Week of 9 March						
Podcast 7	Week of 20 Apr						
Podcast 8	Week of 1 June						
Podcast 9	Week of 13 July						
Podcast 10	Week of 24 Aug						
Podcast 11	Week of 5 Oct						
Podcast 12	Week of 16 Nov						
Podcast 13	Week of 14 Dec						
Podcast 14	Week of 18 Jan 2027						
Podcast 15	Week of 22 Feb						

10.4. Annex 4. Event Plan

The Event Plan is available at the WP4 folder on SharePoint: [RM Framework social media podcasts events.xlsx](#)

EVENTS TIMETABLE _ TEMPLATE										
Event Nr.	Topics or KERs in focus	Aim	Target group 1	Target group 2	Type of event	Format(s)	Responsible partner(s)	Date	Venue	No. of participants
Online user events										
Online user event 1								M13		
Online user event 2								M15		
Online user event 3								M17		
Online user event 4								M19		
Online user event 5								M21		
Online user event 6								M23		
Offline user events: 1 per partner country										
Offline user event 1 (combined with outreach event 1)					RM Framework event			M9- M10	Budapest, HU	
Offline user event 2 (combined with outreach event 2)					RM Framework event			M23-M24	Brussels, BE	
Offline user event 3										

D4.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities (PDEC)

Offline user event 4										
Offline user event 5										
Offline user event 6										
Offline user event 7										
Offline user event 8										
Offline user event 9										
Offline user event 10										
Outreach events										
Outreach event 1					RM Framework event			M9-10	Budapest, HU	
Outreach event 2					RM Framework event			M23-M24	Brussels, BE	

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10.5. Annex 5. PDEC monitoring table

PDEC MONITORING_TEMPLATE											
Nr	Partner	Activity type	Title	Date	Location (city, country)	Primary audience	Primary audience no.	Secondary audience	Secondary audience no.	Link	Comments
Article 1											
Article 2											
Article 3											
....											

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